

TRANSFORMATION OF LINGUOPOETIC MEANS IN THE TRANSLATION PROCESS: LINGUISTIC AND AESTHETIC ASPECTS

Hoshimjon Kuchkorov,
Chirchiq State Pedagogical University
Senior Lecturer, Department of Uzbek Literary Studies

Abstract

This article examines the issue of changes in linguopoetic means in the process of translating literary texts from a linguistic and aesthetic perspective. Translation transformations, including lexical, grammatical and stylistic changes, are analyzed. It also presents considerations on the features of translating literary texts, the role of linguistics in literary translation, literary translation, translation theory and practice, and linguopoetic analysis of literary translation.

Keywords: literary translation, text, language, linguopoetic means, translation transformation, linguistic aspects, aesthetic aspects, stylistic equivalence, poetic discourse.

LINGVOPOETIK VOSITALARNING TARJIMA JARAYONIDA TRANSFORMATSIYASI: LINGVISTIK VA ESTETIK ASPEKTLAR

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada adabiy matnlar tarjimasi jarayonida lingvopoetik vositalarning o'zgarishi masalasi lingvistik va estetik nuqtai nazardan ko'rib chiqilgan. Tarjima transformatsiyalari, jumladan, leksik, grammatik va stilistik o'zgarishlar tahlil etilgan. Shuningdek, badiiy matnlarni tarjima qilish xususiyatlari, tilshunoslikning badiiy tarjimada tutgan o'rni, badiiy tarjima, tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyoti, badiiy tarjimaning lingvopoetik tahlili bo'yicha mulohazalar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: badiiy tarjima, matn, til, lingvopoetik vositalar, tarjima transformatsiyasi, lingvistik aspektlar, estetik aspektlar, stilistik ekvivalentlik, poetik diskurs.

ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ЛИНГВОПОЭТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ПЕРЕВОДА: ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ И ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается вопрос об изменении лингвопоэтических средств при переводе художественных текстов с лингвистических и эстетических позиций. Анализируются переводческие трансформации, включая лексические, грамматические и стилистические изменения. Также излагаются соображения об особенностях перевода художественных текстов, роли лингвистики в художественном переводе, художественном переводе, теории и практике перевода, а также лингвопоэтическом анализе художественного перевода.

Ключевые слова: художественный перевод, текст, язык, лингвопоэтические средства, переводческая трансформация, лингвистические аспекты, эстетические аспекты, стилистическая эквивалентность, поэтический дискурс.

Literary translation is not only the process of transferring a text from one language to another, but also the preservation of its aesthetic and emotional impact. Linguvopoetic devices are devices created using the poetic capabilities of the language, which ensure the beauty of a literary work. In the process of translation, these devices often undergo transformation, since there is an asymmetry between languages.

Linguvopoetics, that is, the direction that studies the poetic and aesthetic functions of language devices in a literary text, occupies a central place in translation theory. Paulo Coelho's work "The Alchemist" occupies a significant place in world literature and has been translated into more than 80 languages. There are also several translations into Uzbek, including the 2003 edition by Ahmad Otaboy and other versions. This article analyzes the transformation of linguvopoetic devices in the translation process from a linguistic (semantic, syntactic, lexical) and aesthetic (impact, cultural adaptation) perspective, using this work as an example.

Linguvopoetics is a field that studies the role of language tools in creating an aesthetic effect in a literary work. In the translation process, these tools undergo transformation, since each language has its own characteristics. For example, the semantic load of a metaphor or symbol may not be fully preserved in the target language. The work "The Alchemist" contains many philosophical and symbolic elements, and translators used different strategies to translate them into Uzbek.

Translation is a complex mental process in which different cultures and traditions, folk customs, different ways of thinking, understanding, the image of the world of the people through languages, different histories and literatures are reflected, and as a

result, a new text is created in a form characteristic of the language being translated. One of the most important factors in the translator's work is the genre of the translated text, since its characteristics are directly related to the content and means of linguistic expression. In the field of translation studies, the laws of text translation are studied depending on the genre, and this constitutes a special theory of translation. "Special translation theory is a part of general translation theory, which is aimed at studying the features of the translation process of texts of different genres, the influence of speech forms and their practical conditions" [1: 413].

When studying or describing the features of translation, three main factors should be taken into account:

1. Determining the style of the original text, since the style of the text can affect the features of the translation process and force the translator to use special methods.

2. Determining the stylistic features of the original language, which helps to choose the means of expressing the text correctly in the target language.

3. As a result of the interaction of these two factors, it is possible to find suitable features of translation, which depend on the common and distinctive aspects between the stylistic features of the original language and the target language, creating suitable conditions for the translation process. Thus, the theory of special translation studies the influence of a certain style of the original language and a style close to it in the target language, as well as the interaction of these two linguistic speech phenomena.

Linguistic aspects. The linguistic aspect includes language structure and meaning transfer in the translation process. In the work "The Alchemist", linguopoetic means - metaphor, image, symbol - play a key role. Their semantic equivalence must be ensured during translation.

Semantic transformation. Semantics - meaning transfer. The concept of "Personal Legend" is central in the work. In English, "Personal Legend" is a person's destiny and dream. In the Uzbek translation, Ahmad Otoboy translated it as "Personal Legend", which is semantically correct, but the word "legend" can have a legendary meaning in Uzbek, which changes the aesthetic effect.

Example: Original: "It's what you have always wanted to accomplish. Everyone, when they are young, knows what their Personal Legend is."

Uzbek translation (Ahmad Otoboy): "Bu siz doimo amalga oshirishni xohlagan narsangiz. Har bir inson yoshligida o'z shaxsiy afsonasini biladi." (It's something you always wanted to accomplish. Everyone knows their own personal legend when they're young.)

Here, semantic equivalence is preserved, but the philosophical depth of “Personal Legend” takes on a mythical tone in Uzbek through “afsona”, which slightly changes the universal fateful aspect of the original meaning.

In other translations (for example, in anonymous versions), “Shakhsiy taqdir” is used, which gives a more philosophical meaning, but loses the original symbolic element.

Each style has its own linguistic and grammatical translation characteristics. In particular, the artistic style, that is, the translation of works of art, also has its own translation characteristics. This chapter considers artistic texts and their translation characteristics.

The artistic style is associated with art. The basis of this style is visual imagination, which is expressed through spiritual and material arts. A text is created in the artistic style.

Each work of art is the author's worldview and a figurative reflection of reality. A work of art has an individual and figurative image of the world of the author, which has an intellectual and emotional impact on the reader. “When describing reality, the writer necessarily expresses his point of view and attitude to reality. For this purpose, he mixes reality with artistic imagination” [2: 72]. This situation is reflected in the artistic text. “A literary text” is defined by G.V. As Stepanov wrote, “it seems impossible to us to express meaning through synonymous speech. The artistic content cannot be expressed independently of the semantic shades of the language” [3: 27].

Syntactic and lexical changes. Syntactic structure is important in the translation process. The work contains many short, philosophical sentences: “The Soul of the World is nourished by people's happiness.”

Uzbek translation: “Dunyo ruhini insonlarning baxti oziqlantiradi.”(The soul of the world is nourished by the happiness of people.)

Here the syntax is preserved, but in the lexical selection "nourished" is given as "nourishes", which strengthens the anthropomorphic metaphor.

Lexically, the work contains elements of Arabic and Portuguese culture. “Alchemist” – “Alkimyogar”, which is correct, but in Uzbek the word “alkimyo” can give a chemical meaning, which changes the aesthetic effect.

In the translation, paralinguistic elements, such as intonation and rhythm, change. For example, in the work, the shepherd's internal monologues are rhythmic, while in the Uzbek translation they are lengthened due to the syntactic features of the Uzbek language.

Aesthetic aspects. The aesthetic aspect is the preservation of the literary effect. In the translation process, aesthetics undergoes transformation through cultural adaptation.

Another example: Original: "When you want something, all the universe conspires in helping you achieve it."

Uzbek translation: "Biror narsani chin dildan xohlasangiz, butun koinot sizga yordam berish uchun ittifoq qiladi." (When you truly want something, the entire universe conspires to help you.)

Aesthetically, this sentence is the central motto of the work. The translation preserves the rhythm, but the rendering of "conspires" as "alliances" preserves the mysterious aesthetic.

The main distinguishing feature of the literary text is its anthropocentric (human-centered) means of influence. That is, the depiction of the world in a work of art is primarily aimed at understanding man, and all other artistic events show the laws of human life. Even in the genres of narrative and myth, images reflect the laws of human life, that is, they express them in a symbolic and diagnostic form, and the spirit of the "I" is clearly felt in them. The author expresses his subjective point of view through images. And the reader, as a subject of spiritual and practical activity, perceives aesthetic images of artistic reality and enriches them according to his personal attitude.

Thus, the categories of author - character - reader constitute the anthropocentric semantic structure of a work of art.

It is worth noting that different readers perceive different meanings depending on the spiritual and aesthetic potential of a work of art. The perception of artistic information and the interpretation of the text depend on the qualities, tastes and interests of the reader. Reading a work of art is a creative process, in which the imagination of an individual character, general abstract aspects of humanity and the laws of the social system are reflected. The same work is understood and interpreted differently in different periods.

Evidence shows that the main feature of literary texts is the polysemy of their lexical means. In lyrical works, the polysemy of words is clearly visible, which is expressed by the synonymy or alternation of words. Polysemy is also observed in short and collected texts. In some cases, the polysemy of words is the result of the author's creative thought, which leaves the reader to evaluate and draw conclusions. At the same time, despite the polysemy of the lexical features of any literary work, there is an invariable core, which allows for the full and perfect execution of the translation.

Linguistic aspects constitute the main part of translation transformations. They arise due to differences in language systems and are manifested at the lexical, grammatical and syntactic levels.

At the syntactic level, transposition is widespread: the length and structure of the sentence are changed. Grammatical transformations, including antonymic translation (transformation of a negative structure into a positive one), additions and abbreviations, ensure the naturalness of the text.

Aesthetic aspects are aimed at preserving the emotional and artistic impact of linguopoetic means. They include figurative language and cultural adaptation.

Literary translation is seen as a two-level monolith: code-schematic structure and analysis from the author's point of view.

In most cases, a literary text is multifunctional. "It can combine several tasks, for example, aesthetic, philosophical and social tasks" [4: 14-15].

A literary text is the result of a creative process, reflecting the author's creative ideas; it is rich in various types of information - real, emotional and educational. A literary text expresses the linguistic and national world of the author and the people who speak it. A literary text is characterized by diversity, metaphor, artistry and expressiveness. "The main task of a literary text is not only to convey information, but also to have an aesthetic and emotional impact on the reader or listener" [5: 21]. This idea is also supported by V.V. Sdobnikov and O.V. Petrova: "A literary text differs in the nature of the information it conveys, since it usually contains intellectual, emotional and aesthetic information. This, of course, requires special methods of transmission, and information is conveyed through intellectual, emotional and aesthetic impact" [6: 356]. Thus, if the main task of a logical text is to provide information, then a literary text, along with providing information, has an aesthetic effect on the reader and listener. Therefore, the author of a literary work must use a wider variety of means of expression, which creates many difficulties in translation. Abdurakhmonova R.J. writes about the difficulties of translation: "When translating a literary text, the criteria for translation increase significantly. The translator must meet more requirements, so that he creates a text that fully corresponds to the original text in a foreign culture" [7: 32]. Indeed, translating a literary text is difficult and requires not only language knowledge from the translator, but also translation skills and abilities. The main difficulty of translating a literary text is that the translator must preserve not only the meaning, but also its tone and emotional tone. Thus, how the work is perceived by the reader depends on the translation. Therefore, the main task of the translator is not only

to convey the original textual information, but also to preserve effective means of expression.

Cultural adaptation and aesthetic losses. In the Uzbek translation, elements of Arabic culture (Fatima, desert) are close to the Uzbek reader, but Portuguese culture (Andalusia) is alien. Translators made adaptations, for example, they kept “sycamore” as “sikamor”, but explained the aesthetic image in detail.

Aesthetic losses: The poetic rhythm in the work is changed by using shorter sentences in English, and longer sentences in Uzbek. This reduces the impact.

Concrete examples and comparisons. In this section, we will compare several fragments of the work.

Example 1: From the Prologue.

Original: “The Alchemist picked up a book that someone in the caravan had brought. Leafing through the pages, he found a story about Narcissus.”

Uzbek translation (Ahmad Otaboy): “Alkimyogar karvonning birida kimdir olib kelgan kitobni oldi. Varag'lab, Narcissus haqidagi hikoyani topdi.”(The alchemist picked up a book that someone had brought with him in one of the caravans. Flipping through the pages, he found the story of Narcissus.)

Linguistic: Semantics preserved, syntax adapted to the Uzbek language.

Aesthetic: The symbol of the story (self-love) is preserved, but the word “varag'lab” in Uzbek is simple, losing the poetics of the original.

Example 2: Shepherd's dream.

Original: “He had the same dream that night as a week ago, and once again he had awakened before it ended.”

Uzbek translation: “U o'sha kecha bir hafta oldingi tushni ko'rди va yana tugashidan oldin uyg'ondi.”(He had a dream that night from a week ago and woke up again before it was over.)

Transformation: The short sentence is preserved, but aesthetically the mysterious effect of the dream is stronger in Uzbek, because the word “tush” has a cultural connotation.

Another translation: “He saw again the dream he had a week ago and woke up before it ended.” Here the differences are lexical – “that night” is added, which changes the rhythm.

Example 3: Philosophical dialogue.

Original: “Because I don't live in either my past or my future. I'm interested only in the present.”

Uzbek translation: “Chunki men o'tmishimda ham, kelajagimda ham yashamayman. Meni faqat hozirgi payt qiziqtiradi.”(Because I don't live in my past or my future. I'm only interested in the present moment.)

The transformation of linguopoetic means in the translation process requires consideration of linguistic asymmetry and aesthetic requirements. Linguistic aspects serve to preserve natural equivalence, and aesthetic aspects serve to preserve emotional impact. Linguopoetic means undergo linguistic and aesthetic transformation in the translation process, but as can be seen in the example of “The Alchemist”, the translators managed to preserve semantic equivalence. Aesthetic losses arise due to cultural differences.

REFERENCES

1. Комиссаров, В.Н. Современное переводоведение. Учебное пособие / В.Н. Комиссаров. – М.: ЭТС., 2002. – 424 с.
2. Гальперин, И.Р. Перевод и стилистика // Теория и методика учебного процесса. / И.Р. Гальперин. – Москва, 1960. – 236с.
3. Степанов Г.В. Язык. Литература. Поэтика. – М., 1988.– 383 с.
4. Левый, И. Искусство перевода / И. Левый. – М.: Прогресс, 1974. – 280 с.
5. Солодуб, Ю.П. Теория и практика художественного перевода: учеб. пособие для студ. лингв. фак. вузов / Ю.П. Солодуб, Ф.Б. Альбрехт, А.Ю. Кузнецов. – М.: Академия, 2005. – 304 с.
6. Сдобников, В.В. Теория перевода: учебник для студентов лингвистических вузов и факультетов иностранных языков / В.В. Сдобников, О.В. Петрова. – М.: АСТ: Восток-Запад, 2007. – 448 с
7. Абдрахманова, Р.Дж. Художественный перевод (лингвистические аспекты): учебное пособие для студентов старших курсов переводческих отделений. / Р.Дж. Абдрахманова. – Бишкек: Изд-во КРСУ, 2014. – 86 с.
8. Коэльо П. Алхимёгар. (Аҳмад Отабой таржимаси). – Т.: Маърифат-Мадаккор, 2003. – 63 б.